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Review Article

A Review on The Role Of 3d Printing in Pharmacy

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of 3D printing technology in the pharmaceutical industry has opened new horizons in the research and development of printed materials and devices. The main benefits of 3D printing technology lie in the production of small batches of medicines, each with tailored dosages, shapes, sizes, and release characteristics. The pharmaceutical industry is moving ahead at a rapid pace. Modern technology has enabled the development of novel dosage forms for targeted therapy. However, the fabrication of novel dosage forms at industrial scale is limited and the industry still runs on conventional drug delivery systems, especially modified tablets. The manufacture of medicines in this way may finally lead to the concept of medicines becoming a reality. This chapter provides an overview of how 3D printed technology has exit personalized ended from initial unit operations to developed final products. Compared to traditional preparation technologies, 3D printing offers flexibility in the design of complex 3D structures within drugs, the adjustment of drug doses and combinations, and rapid manufacturing and prototyping, enabling precise control of drug release to meet a wide range of clinical needs, a high degree of flexibility and creativity to personalize pharmaceuticals, and a significant reduction in preparation development time, driving a breakthrough in drug manufacturing technology and transforming the way we design, manufacture, and use drugs. Three-dimensional printing technologies have been used to manufacture a variety of medicinal products, such as immediate-release tablets, controlled-release tablets, dispersible films, microneedles, implants, and transdermal patches . The main 3D printing technologies used in pharmaceuticals are BJ-3DP, FDM, SSE, and MED in material extrusion, and SLA . Table 1 describes the characteristics of these technologies at each stage of drug preparation and assesses the advantages and disadvantages of each technology.

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INTRODUCTION

New ideas in the field of drugs are always being design, improved material understanding, manufacturing technology, and procedures that guarantee excellent quality of dosage styles. Active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) contain a variety of physicochemical and biopharmaceutical features that need to be taken into account and researched via each in the process of being developed. Additional materials must be Additionally studied in order to produce the optimal dosage form the development of patient-centred drug products has received a lot of attention over the past ten years. It had direction. On cutting-edge technology methods and innovative dosage formulations. Increasing demand for customized gadgets along with an increase in the greatest advancements in personalized medicine are driven by technological innovation, as evidenced, for example, by the creation of small series of tailored dosages and prosthetics created to order satisfy the patients' anatomical requirements. Three-dimensional printing (3DP), among the many breakthroughs introduced to the pharmaceutical and biomedical markets, is thought to be the most revolutionary and potent. This method is regarded as a flexible one. A tool for accurate gadget manufacture. It functions as a technology for creating novel dosage forms, engineering tissues and organs, and simulating diseases. Three-dimensional printing is one of the fields of technology, art, and science that is now advancing the fastest. Increases the applications' scope. The International Standard Organization provided a definition of "three-dimensional printing" (ISO)described as: "Fabrication of items through the deposition of a material utilizing a print head, nozzle, or other printer technology." In This methodology is one of the methods of additive manufacturing, as opposed to the more popular subtractive and formative manufacturing methodologies. In additive

manufacturing (AM), materials are assembled layer by layer to create items from data from 3D models. Rapid prototyping (RP) is the term for the use of AM in practise. Its benefits include the ease with which a product can be modified at a designed time and at a designed cost. Level, the potential production of tiny items, individualized product lines, or impossibly complex architectures using subtractive methods Since 2012, the use of 3D printing in research and engineering has increased. The quantity of academic papers from 59 in 2012 to 1573 in 2017 that were listed in the Web of Science Core Collection and had the terms "B3D printing" or "B3D printed" in the title. In addition, these works received 12,411 citations throughout the same time span, up from 209 at the beginning. No results are returned when the search results are limited to the pharmacy/pharmacology category in 2012, but 77 entries were identified up until 2017, indicating a significant interest in 3DP methods in pharmaceutical sciences. The most recent advancements and successes in the fields of pharmaceutical and biological research are the focus of this review. from the works of literature that have been released in the previous three years. The innovative methods used in the creation of solid dose Though transdermal medication administration and biological applications are also concentrated, forms for customized therapy are given special attention. Implants, surgical models, bioprinter materials, and bio robotics are also highlighted as examples of additive manufacturing techniques. A specific attempt is made to highlight the progress of bioprinting as the concurrent development of additive manufacturing utilised in pharmaceutical technology and bioprinting is discussed and compared. Although there are not many regulations accessible at this time due to the pharmaceutical uses of additive manufacturing still being in the early stages of development and implementation, the key challenges that the FDA introduced in 2017 are discussed.

History

The concept of 3DP has developed since Pierre A. L. Giraud first outlined the technique in the early 1970s of the 20th centuries. Application of powdered material followed by solidification of each layer under the influence of a high intensity laser. In this instance, melting materials like plastics or metals might possibly be utilised to prepare objects. early 1980s in the following is the name of the patent: BA moulding procedure for producing a three-dimensional object in layers, in his description of a Carl Deckard created the technique of "selective laser sintering," which uses a laser to solidify a powdery bed of sand that has been bound by various compounds (SLS). Chuck Hull's first commercially successful invention was stereolithography (SLA). This technique was based on the UV light-induced photopolymerization of liquid resin. Towards the end of the 1980s, Scott Crump submitted a fused Deposition modelling (FDM) is a method for creating objects using thermoplastic material. the 1990s Three-dimensional printing processes, developed by MIT scientist Emanuel Sachs and colleagues, are based on combining the chosen powder regions by binding material[5,6].The presents the most significant developments in 3D printing for pharmaceutical and biological applications.

How It Works

During the nearly 40 years of 3DP history, numerous various technologies were created and

advanced in line with progress. The three main techniques are extrusion, liquid solidification, and powder solidification. During the nearly 40 years of 3DP history, numerous various technologies were created and advanced in line with progress. The three main techniques are extrusion, liquid solidification, and powder solidification. Each 3D printer operates in a unique manner. Mode requires enough material to solidify, followed by the creation of the object. Despite the variety of 3DP techniques, the process of preparing a 3D-printed object involves numerous steps: using computer-aided design software to create 3D objects and optimising their shape in accordance with printer specifications, the export of 3D models to a widely used and printer-friendly file format, such as STL, which only After importing the file into the programme and creating the layers that will be printed, 3D geometry is created in the form of each vertex position data or OBJ in which additional information about polygonal faces or colour texture are coded. The printed layer's height essentially determines the quality of the 3D model. the time spent printing the product, the materials used, and the subsequent application (or) Of the material layers devoted to the particular printing technique. The progression of 3D printed objects is depicted in the use of 3D printing techniques is becoming more prevalent in pharmaceutical and medical applications due to the possibility of quickly creating custom items that can be used in individualised counselling or treatment.

Figure- Vision of 3D printing

It will Rise from Powder. Based on the concept described in, the first 3DP approach utilised in the formulation of pharmaceutical dosage forms "Threedimensional printing techniques" patent. Similar to desktop inkjet, the printing process operates in a similar manner. Drop on Solid Deposition, often known as DOS or Power Bed Jetting, is a printing technique. Ink spray from the print head causes the ink to bind. The free powder layer beneath the unbound powder particles acts as a support material to stop overhanging or porous structures from collapsing. Each stage of the formation of the object is lowered, a free powder layer is deposited using a roller or a powder jetting system, and the operation is continued the initial printers featured commercially available print heads that were thermal or piezoelectric and provided the bonding agent. Ink or other materials can be dissolved or distributed with active medicinal ingredients and/or mod- erasing agents. Dispersed throughout the powder bed. This method was chosen because it can apply excipients that are frequently used in traditional formulation methods, such as wet granulation, and it is similar to such processes. pharmaceutical technology, particularly formulations for solid dosage forms One benefit of this approach is the ability to precisely place the drug dose or alter the excipients within the powdery bed to produce many compartments with various compositions or modes of action. The characteristics of the powder and ink have an impact on the product quality attributes. Particle size, powder bed flowability, cohesive force between particles, and a component of the printer, or powder wettability, all have a significant impact on layer height. More intricate and precise manufacture of structures with slight mass and dosage fluctuations is achieved by using lower layer heights and subsequent layer applications. The solvents, APIs, or modifying excipients used in the ink might alter the viscosity, droplet size, and affect the effectiveness of binds

powder. Process variables including printing speed, droplet volume, and distance from the powder bed are crucial for the creation of a product and can affect how well the powder bonds, particularly between layers in the Z axis. They might have a negative impact on the print lets' mechanical strength. Following printing, other actions including drying, removing any remaining solvents, and unbound powder removal should be done Various solids were prepared using the DOS approach. Methods like implants containing levofloxacin, rifampicin, or rifampicin and isoniazid, among others displaying a changed or irregular API release. The modified- release chlorpheniramine and acetaminophen tablets Additionally, tablets with linear release characteristics were created. Examples of 3D-printed medications created using various 3D printing techniques are method of manufacturing Powder solidification, effect reference, and dosage form of the API Drop upon a sturdy implant Powdered isoniazid. Tablets Captopril Powders: Maltodextrin and Maltitol Ink: Polyvinylpyrrolidone and Water rapid tablet dispersion Selective laser sintering of tablets that are odourless Copolymer of paracetamol, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, vinylpyrrolidone, and vinyl acetate Easily dissolved pills with quick medication release Tablets for Stereolithography and Liquid Solidification Paracetamol 4-Aminosalicylic \Saci Diphenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphine oxide, Poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate, and Poly(ethylene glycol) 300Coordinated release Dental SG resin, Xylitol, Mannitol, and Trehalose Microneedles Insulin Skin administration of insulin Ropinirole HCl Irakere 2959 Drop on Drop Tablets Poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate Mechanism for Ficken diffusion API release White beeswax Ficken diffusion (10 tablets) Fenofibrate API release Ropinirole HCl Irakere 2959 Drop on Drop Tablets Poly (ethylene glycol) diacrylate Mechanism for Fiskian

diffusion API release Fenofibrate tablets, white beeswax, a Fiskian diffusion API release mechanism, and techniques based on extrusion Orodispersible film modelling via fused deposition Polyvinyl alcohol with aripiprazole rapid breakdown and disintegration Theophylline tablets made of hydroxypropyl cellulose, Crospovidone, sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose, and triacetin instant release At-room temperature extrusion Tablets that float Dipyridamole Microcrystalline cellulose, Lactose, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone, and Hydroxypropyl Methyl cellulose gastrofloating, sustained-release dose formulates- compart- \smenttablet Nifedypine, \captopril, \sGlipizidMicrocrystalline cellulose, Sodium starch glycolate, Croscarmellose sodium, Dmannitol, Polyethylene glycol 6000, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, volume.

Changing From Liquid To Solid

The concept of making objects by solidifying liquid is analogous to the process for solidifying powder. Spraying of Bink creates droplets that are then placed on thin layers and cured by high

energy light or cooling air. Drop on drop (DOD) or Poly jet technique needs to use extra material to support overhang geometries because there isn't a powdery bed present. During printing, the print platform bed is lowered and the print head travels along the X and Y axes. after each layer of the material has been deposited, along the Z axis by the layer height. Different This technique's technical innovations made it possible to print in full colour on multiple materials. The characteristics of the spraying material influence both the printed product's quality and the curing process. The first resources Wax was employed in these processes. Modified release dosage forms were employed in pharmaceutical technology. Formulation, and currently found use in 3DP technology. To prevent quick solidification, molten wax was sprayed over the construction platform in the heated chamber. By using 3D material jetting of molten wax to create matrix tablets containing beeswax and fenofibrate, Koula et al.

Figure:- changing from liquid to solid

discovered the impact of custom geometries (honeycomb architecture with varied infill ratios) on the dissolution profile. The geometry of the honeycomb's cell size and the wettability of the substance was discovered to influence the dissolution profile from constant weight pills. As honeycomb surface and diameter rose, so did the amount of released medicine.in the case of

honeycomb channels of a medium size. Honeycomb's tiniest dimensions, the medium for disintegration can penetrate them. Was insufficient, and the surface of the broadest honeycomb on the tablets was smaller than the middle-sized structure, which led to Drug dissolution decreased in both situations. This occurrence when combined with a variety of

materials, can enable the manufacturing of customised medications. geometry. In this process, photosensitive polymers may also be utilised, and UV light is used to solidify the layers. To Analyse the potential for using photopolymer resin in 3D printing of medications, including tablets with ropinirole HCl and polyethyleneIrgacure 2959 was created as a photo initiator using PEGDA (polyethylene glycol) diacrylate) and a low concentration of oxygen, which can stop the healing processes.

Extrusion-Based Methods:

Basics Extrusion of semisolids and hot melt extrusion (HME). This technical approach is based on the increasing accessibility of small-scale and reasonably priced equipment. Extrusion of semisolid, or semimolten materials (gels, pastes) at room temperature or higher, and extrusion of molten thermoplastic rodshape material, are essentially two types of printing method that can be distinguished (filament). The material is spread out on the build platform in successive layers in both modes after being extruded from the nozzle. The print head's distance from the build plate and the nozzle orifice diameter both contribute to the defined dimension of the printed route. The quality of the printed product is influenced by these two factors as well as print speed. When the print head or print platform moves along the Z axis at a distance equal to the layer height, another layer is applied. The technological solution of 3D printers depends on the printing medium.

Filament: The Principal Obstacle

Extrusion of molten thermoplastic material serves as the foundation for fused deposition modelling. measurements of the filaments in the Standard commercially available print heads are used with a range of 1.75 mm and 2.85-3mm. Common filaments a reconstructed of thermoplastic polymers like poly (lactic acid), poly (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene), high impact polystyrene

(HIPS), and polyethylene terephthalate glycol-modified nylon, (PET-G). Some are offered for sale commercially. Despite being made from medical-grade polymers like PLA and PVA, high-quality filaments, the prepared filaments There are currently no commercially available APIs made from pharmaceutical grade polymers. The heat stability of the impregnated API must be taken into consideration when preparing drug-loaded filaments. In the FDM process, the filament is pushed towards the heat end under the guidance of gears. It melts and is pushed. by unmeted filament, via the nozzle aperture. The nozzle orifice's diameter, which ranges from 0.2 to 0.4 mm, affects the printed object's resolution. Altho

Shape Matters

The medication dissolving rate is also influenced by the form of the printlets. Goyanes et al. offered paracetamol tablets in various forms with constant surfaces. The formulations with pyramid shapes had the fastest dissolving rates. Has the highest surface area to volume ratio, whereas cylindrical or spherical geometries have the lowest ratio. Were distinguished by having the slowest dissolving ratio. It was also suggested to modify the tablet's design by including the extra channels to hasten the dissolution of hydrochlorothiazide. channels that are square in shape and have a diameter During the designing phase, were embedded at intervals of 0.2 to 1.0 mm. The dissolving data showed that the drug release was essentially accelerated by a channel of size 0.6 mm, which satisfies the pharmacopoeia criteria for instant release products Arafat and colleagues suggested a different creative tablet technique. Tablets were made up of 9 bridging pieces spaced apart. The disintegration and dissolution time was impacted by the various block and gap sizes . The intended strategy is Application of an intriguing substitute for disintegrants to speed up tablet disintegration.

Two Minds Are Superior To One

In a dual head extrusion method, the print head is fitted with two independent stepper motors and heating chambers, enabling the use of two materials with various melting points. Okwuona The delayed release tablets were made by et al. (51) with a PVP polymer core that was theophylline-loaded and printed by a single extruder, and an outside complimentary Eudragit® L shell. By using the second printing extruder, thicknesses were pre-pared, increasing from 0.17 to 0.87 mm. The thickness of the shell that was 0.52 mm necessary to ensure adequate core protection in the acidic medium. Twin layer modified release tablets can also be created using a dual head solution. Li et al 's concept for a Duo Tablet-dosage device shape constructed with an exterior and interior compartment.

Using Semisolids To Extrude

If you use the extrusion technique to print semisolid or semi-molten materials (gels, pastes) at room temperature or above, in contrast to FDM, some adjustments have been made to print head construction . Through which the bulk is ejected orifice using a syringe plunger, screw, or compressed air pressure. Although this approach makes it possible to create dosage forms with a large drug content, it also necessitates a drying phase. Alter the integrity of the product. Tablets of immediate release paracetamol containing 80% of the active ingredient were created using pharmaceutical-grade excipients that adhere to pharmacopoeia standards. Standards. The redesigned release systems were also ready. In order to extend the gastric residence period, Li Q et al. created gastrofloating tablets that contain dipyrindamole. investigation of in vitro buoyancy found that formulations with 30 and 50% infilling rates floated for up to 12 hours. Polypill can be prepared as a multiactive solid dosage form using a multi-syringe printing technique. Including three or five APIs that were issued with various kinetic characteristics.

Therapy Centred On The Patient

3D printing techniques offer a wide range of uses in medical, including the use of numerous materials. to create spatial systems for tissue engineering and for the preparation of dose forms such tablets, capsules, implants, or dispersible films by a pharmacy. as before as previously said, tablets are the dosage forms that are created the most. Although they can be produced in a variety of geometries, only a small number of dosages for each API are offered on an industrial basis. The notion of more customised medications been created for many years, but its significance has never been higher than it is right now. The necessity of development individualised medication through patients' prudent drug Use Neterogenous character of diseases is the source of difficulty in determining the appropriate dosage, which is a topic of intense discussion. Intervention in therapy. The treatment Some of the justifications for changing the dosage form and dose of the active ingredient, particularly for specific age groups, are therapeutic failures or restrictions on therapeutic effects. The right dose forms must be chosen while taking into account not only physicochemical characteristics but also target demographic and treated condition .

Use of 3D Printers In Community Pharmacies And Hospitals: The use of 3D printers in community pharmacies and hospitals would take pharmaceutical compounding to a whole new level. The quantity of medicines supplied, their shape, colour, and taste, as well as the dose of the active ingredient, are particularly crucial when treating juvenile patients. Additionally, some 3D printing techniques, such as fused deposition modelling, where APIs are Without any additional processing, such as film coating, taste masking is possible when introduced into polymer matrix. Containing good repeatability, precision, content uniformity, and quick API dissolution, Scouters et al. manufactured taste-masked dosage forms in the

form of Star mix® Haribo jelly beans with indomethacin using this 3D printing technique. Patient acceptance is influenced by the tablet's size and form, particularly in terms of swallowing issues. Not only because of swallowing issues, but also because of manipulation issues, tablet shape is very important to senior people. Goyanes et al. looked into impact of various tablet shapes, including sphere, torus, disc, capsule, and tilted diamond shape, on patients' moods over time of the swallowing capacity with care. The doughnutshaped, or torus, pills were discovered to be the simplest to swallow. Due to their resemblance to traditional dose forms, tablets with a typical shape were also considered acceptable. In the same team's earlier research indicated that these form differences only marginally affect the dissolving behaviour, hence there must to be flexibility in selecting the geometry for different patients. Applying chosen soluble or non-soluble excipients, as well as defining the desired geometry and internal structure of the printed dosage forms, allows for more exact control over dissolving behaviour when employing 3D printing technology. Although it could be employed in hospital pharmacies, this possibility should only be taken advantage of by healthcare experts because it necessitates knowledge of the pharmacokinetics of the active ingredient and the patient's health. Although solid oral dose forms have received the most research attention, a transdermal drug delivery system was also made using 3D printing. Using fluorescein, Luzuriaga et al. printed microneedles.

From Patient Home To Production Scale

Although additive manufacturing techniques are still relatively new to society and the idea that patients will print their own medical devices is still rather futuristic, the 3D printing of medications in-patient facilities is heavily debated in scholarly communities. Having access to medications at one's own home is somewhat remote. The biggest

barrier to putting this into practise is the safety and quality of the drugs are a concern for the patients. Patients or those providing them with medical care must receive detailed instruction on how to operate a printer and spot potential quality problems with self-printed medications. However, this strategy may be advantageous for the Patients participated more actively in their care, which was proven to be therapeutically advantageous. On the other side, it might also result in some downsides such as losing control over unfavourable effects when creating polypills with multiple active ingredients in a single drug. As was previously indicated, 3D printing may be rather easily incorporated into the pharmacy's pharmaceutical compounding process. It appears that fused deposition modelling has the due to its proximity, high-quality API-loaded documentation, database with items to print, and medically-educated Staff members, such as pharmacists, are able to print the final dosage form with a de-fined architecture and active substance dose. The Manufacturing API-loaded filaments is not a significant barrier for the pharmaceutical business because hot melt extrusion, the fundamental technique for preparing filaments, is well- established in the sector. Inkjet printable filaments have so far been acquired from a variety of pharmaceutical grade polymers, such as methacrylic acid and derivatives of cellulose poly (ethylene oxide), poly (vinyl alcohol), and poly (ethylene glycol)-vinyl alcohol graft copolymers, as well as poly (vinyl caprolactam)-poly (vinyl acetate) (vinyl acetate) Ethylene vinyl acetate, poly (ethylene glycols), poly (ethylene glycol graft copolymer, and others.

Letter Of Law

The use of three-dimensional printing is expanding quickly. It is distinguished by having a great potential from a pharmaceutical perspective. Even if it is still in the early stages of Taking everything into account, there have been numerous attempts to scale up this technology, and 3DP has proven to

be a successful technique, particularly in personalised medicine. Nevertheless, thorough to make the 3DP approaches industrially practicable for dosage form formulation, more study is still required. Currently, only There is only one FDA-approved product available. The printable goods must adhere to the existing production and quality-control requirements for medical devices and products. The advantages and limitations of 3D printing technology are both demonstrated by recent studies. Consequently, due to the abundance of the elements influencing the effectiveness of computationally developed dosage The necessary regulatory criteria are highly preferred due to the forms and safety of their use. Currently, there are none Legitimate guidelines for design, manufacturing, and quality control considerations. There is a dire requirement to create some rules for this specific category of manufacturing techniques. Technical Considerations, a Food and Drug Administration advice document released in December 2017, the number of recommendations for additively manufactured medical devices takes into account the key components of software and hardware specifications, quality assurance practises, and process validation processes. While other techniques, such as the drop-on-drop method and fused deposition modelling, do not leave residues. It appears that each and every printing processes require unique regulations. It must be emphasised that there are still no laws for pharmaceuticals. Which frequently have more stringent criteria than those for medical equipment. Each of the concerns for devices stated should be medications are also taken into account. Additionally, the presence of API necessitates the consideration of several additional factors. Taking into account potential incompatibilities active ingredient steadiness throughout the print process, etc. Due to the fact that the fused deposition modelling approach uses high-resolution both

times, at a greater temperature during printing and at the filament extrusion step.

Biomedical Application

Since the invention of 3D printing in the 1980s, the impact of additive manufacturing on the biomedical profession has significantly increased. Early 80'. It is because the process allows for the fabrication of specially designed materials with unique architecture and functionality. It became a potent tool for Using biomedical engineering, implants can be manufactured according to the anatomy of each patient. Phantoms for medical planning, education, and illness models. Additionally, additive manufacturing takes cues from nature on how intelligent materials and gadgets form.

Models For Surgical Planning And Training, Phantoms

Medical phantoms continue to be in high demand as tools for numerous diseases' diagnosis and therapy. While For decades, image-driven surgery has been employed extensively, thither demand to render digital images has increased. The application of additive manufacturing of models allows for more precise diagnosis, better assessment, and evaluation of the problematic alterations as well as the examination of organ anatomy specific to a patient. Preoperative planning substantially raises the information that goes beyond specific organ attributes decreases complications and patient mortality. Therefore, it is thought that education and surgical planning are two of the most important technology of 3D printing has been studied Manufacturing of liver models is one instance of using 3D-printed medical models. The increasing need for the demand for using healthy livers increased due to transplants and the scarcity of cadaveric livers. Donors. The safety of both the donor and the recipient can be increased by knowing the anatomy of the biliary tract and circulatory system before surgery. These paediatric models, which

illustrate intricate anatomical concepts like the double-outlet right ventricle, malalignment-type ventricular septal abnormalities, and the range of heterotaxia syndromes, are extremely valuable educational Tools The use of 3D- printed models that faithfully replicate the anatomy and sizes of aorta vessels makes the treatment of aortic

illnesses easier. production of phantoms in additive achieved success introduced in patients with cardiac tumours or hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, when the size of the lesion is the primary factor determining whether to perform partial or complete surgical removal.

Figure- 3d Models For Surgical Planinig And Training

Bio Robotics

Hybrid gadgets influenced by biology Being able to simulate different biological processes has recently received a lot of interest. The biorobots are formed on artificial scaffold made of. From hydrogels or polymer elastomers that hold soft biological stuff like proteins, live cells, or Tissues. Hey can conduct several sorts of movement, such as walking or swimming, and can interact with their surroundings since they are more flexible than typical robots. Rotating devices within such robots that are typically linked to the transformation of chemical energy from hydrolysis to work are the most motivational. Actuators made of cells are often grown on thin, flexible substrates[. Using mammalian cardiac and skeletal models, it is demonstrated that cell contraction results in film deflection and actuation. muscular tissue highlighting the benefits of 3D (bio)printing tissues, the biorobots' organs are in hot demand since they function as little mechanical tools with tissue regeneration capability drug administration. They could aid in understanding the loco-Williams' description of the microbes' driving force and colleagues. They

developed the long flagellar swimmer. Short head and tail made of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)cardiomyocyte-cultured filament. Furthermore, the approach may be used for various things, according to the authors. Het- or optogenetic muscle cells are examples of homotypic cell types.erotypic cell types, including fibroblasts and turtle cardiomyocytes sensing-based intelligent systems, in addition to neurons and muscle cell swimming. Other examples rely on cardiomyocyte seeding on the creation and PDMS membrane of little sphere heart due to a pump's ability to regulate the flow inside a microchannel to a diaphragm's pulsatile action. Despite the fact that cell survival and motility are stella problem, various suggestions to improve such aspects have been presented thus far. Enhancing the contrast is one of them. The cells' traction force by utilising anisotropic alignment, in-the use of electrical stimulation to regulate the rate of manufacturing or contracting for the production of stimuli- responsive robots the use of light-sensitive cells.

Advantages

1. Accurate and precise dosing of potent drugs which are administered at small doses.
2. Reduces cost of production due to lesser material wastage .
3. Narrow therapeutic window. 4. Medication can be tailored to a patient in particular based on genetic variations, ethnic differences, age, gender and environment.
5. High drug loading ability when compared to conventional dosage forms.
6. In case of multi drug therapy with multiple dosing regimen, treatment can be customized to improve patient adherence.
7. Suitable drug delivery for difficult to formulate active ingredients like poor water solubility.
8. Different materials can be used in the 3D models. It makes very easy to create construction models or prototypes for a wide variety of projects within many industries. 9. The products with an excellent surface finish are produced.

Disadvantages

1. The 3D printing technology is currently limited by size limitations. Very large objects are still not possible when built using 3D printers.
2. The cost of buying a 3D printer still does not make its purchase by the average householder possible. Different 3D printers are required in order to print different types of objects and the printers that can manufacture in color are costlier than those that print monochrome objects.
3. As with all new technologies, manufacturing jobs will decrease. This disadvantage can have a large impact to the economies of third world countries especially China, that depend on a large number of low skill jobs .
4. At present, 3D printers can work with approximately 100 different raw materials but

it is not suitable when we compared with the enormous range of raw materials used in traditional manufacturing. More research is required to devise methods to enable 3D printed products to be more durable and robust.

Applications Of 3d Printing

3D Printing has been applied in medicine from long times when first it used to make dental implants and custom prosthetics. The current medical uses of 3D Printing can be organized into several broad categories: tissue and organ fabrication; creating prosthetics, implants, and anatomical models; and pharmaceutical research concerning drug discovery, delivery, and dosage forms.

1. Bio Printing Tissues and Organs

Organ printing takes advantage of 3D printing technology to produce cells, biomaterials, and cell-laden biomaterials individually or in tandem, layer by layer, directly creating 3D tissue-like structures. Researchers have used 3D printers to create a knee meniscus, heart valve, spinal disk, other types of cartilage and bone, and an artificial ear.

2. Customized Implants and Prostheses

Implants and prostheses can be made in nearly any imaginable geometry through the translation of X-ray, MRI, or CT scans into digital 3D print files. This approach has been used to fabricate dental, spinal, and hip implants.

3. Anatomical Models

3D-printed neuro-anatomical models can be particularly helpful to neurosurgeons by providing a representation of some of the most complicated structures in the human body.

4. 3D-Printed Dosage Forms and Drug Delivery Devices

In pharmaceutical industries various techniques have been used and the 3D printing is one of them in pharmaceutical research and fabrication due to the precise control of droplet size and dose, high reproducibility, and ability to produce dosage

forms with complex drug-release profiles. Complex drug manufacturing methods can also be standardized through use of 3D printing to make them simpler and more viable. 3D printing technology could be very important in the development of personalized medicine, too.

5. Unique Dosage Forms

The primary 3D printing technologies used for pharmaceutical production are inkjet-based or inkjet powder-based 3D printing. These technologies offer the ability to create limitless dosage forms that are likely to challenge conventional drug fabrication. 3D printers have already been used to produce many novel dosage forms, such as: microcapsules, hyaluronan-based synthetic extracellular matrices, antibiotic printed micropatterns, mesoporous bioactive glass scaffolds, nano suspensions, and multilayered drug delivery devices.

CONCLUSION

It shows promising results in drug delivery applications. It faces many challenges such as optimization process, improving performance of device for versatile use, selections of appropriate excipients, post treatment method, etc., to improve the performance of 3D printed products' and to expand the application range in novel drug delivery systems. To attain quality of 3D products, some essential parameters necessitate to be optimized like printing rate, printing passes, line velocity of the print head, interval time between two printing layer, distance between the nozzles and the powder layer, etc. It is also important for post process after prototyping like drying (hot air heat, microwaves and infrared) methods, as it has major impact on the quality of the finished 3D Printed products. To increase the drug loading capacity in 3D Printed processed tablet, uniaxial compression and suspension dispersed methodologies are adopted, but this technique suffers from increased complexity and clogging of spray nozzle. The 3D printing of drug delivery

systems and medical devices serves as an attractive tool to produce customized product. Since few years the concept of 3D-printed drug formulation Patient-centric medicine swiftly developed and was aimed at enhancing therapy. the initial medicine approved by the fad Research on oral, or mucosal materials produced by 3D printing technology developed incredibly quickly.as well as topical dose types. This interesting innovation provides formulation flexibility, which is challenging to attain using traditional technical methods. Additional production provides for highly precise API-excipient ratio preparation of various dosage forms in a completely novel way compared to conventional pharmaceutical manufacture Additionally, 3D printing offers the chance to Make medication formulations, multidrug devices, and multifunctional drug delivery systems for individualised therapy with accelerated release characteristics.

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